

IOT based soil nutrient and pH level monitoring and analyzing system using ESP8266 and web-based monitoring

Khader Basha Sk, J. Sri Durga Devi, K. Manoj Kumar, K. Ravi Venkata Naveen, A. Purna Mallikharjuna Rao

Department of CSE – Data Science, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Guntur-522016, A.P, India

To Cite this Article

Khader Basha Sk, J. Sri Durga Devi, K. Manoj Kumar, K. Ravi Venkata Naveen & A. Purna Mallikharjuna Rao (2026). IOT based soil nutrient and pH level monitoring and analyzing system using ESP8266 and web-based monitoring. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 12(SI01), 1049-1054. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19613524>

Article Info

Received: 12 March 2026; Revised: 07 April 2026; Accepted: 10 April 2026.

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KEYWORDS

Internet of Things (IoT), Soil Monitoring, pH Level Detection, Soil Nutrient Analysis, ESP8266, Smart Agriculture

ABSTRACT

In modern agriculture, maintaining optimal soil health is essential for improving crop productivity and ensuring sustainable farming practices. Traditional methods of soil testing involve manual sample collection and laboratory analysis, which are time-consuming, costly and do not provide real-time insights. Farmers often lack continuous information about critical soil parameters such as nutrient and pH level, leading to improper fertilizer usage and reduced crop yield. To address these challenges, the integration of internet of things(iot)technology with embedded systems has emerged as an efficient solution for real-time soil monitoring and analysis. The this paper presents an iot-based soil nutrient and ph level monitoring and analyzing system using esp8266, designed to provide continuous and accurate monitoring of soil conditions. The system utilizes various sensors to measure essential soil parameters, including ph levels and nutrient indicators. These sensors are interfaced with the esp8266 microcontroller, which processes the collected data and transmits it to a web-based dashboard through wi-fi connectivity. The use of iot enables remote access to real-time soil data, allowing farmers and agricultural experts to monitor field conditions from anywhere.the implementation of this system offers several advantages, including reduced manual effort, improved accuracy, and real-time decision-making support. It enables precision agriculture by ensuring optimal soil conditions for crop growth, ultimately leading to increased productivity and resource efficiency. The system is cost-effective, scalable, and suitable for both small-scale and large-scale farming applications. Furthermore, it demonstrates the potential of iot and embedded technologies in transforming traditional agricultural practices into smart and automated systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture plays a vital role in the economic development of many countries, and maintaining soil health is one of the most critical factors influencing crop productivity. Soil contains essential nutrients required for plant growth, and its pH level directly affects the availability of these nutrients. Traditional soil testing methods involve collecting samples and analyzing them in laboratories, which is time-consuming, expensive, and does not provide real-time information. As a result, farmers often make decisions based on assumptions rather than accurate data, leading to inefficient use of fertilizers and reduced crop yield [1].

In recent years, advancements in embedded systems and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies have provided new opportunities for smart agriculture. IoT enables continuous monitoring and real-time data collection from agricultural fields, allowing farmers to make informed decisions. Sensors can be used to measure important soil parameters such as pH level and nutrient content, and this data can be transmitted wirelessly to cloud-based platforms for analysis and visualization. Such systems reduce manual effort and improve the accuracy and efficiency of soil management practices [2]. Additionally, the system provides analysis of soil conditions to determine whether the soil is suitable for cultivation or requires treatment. Based on the sensor data, farmers can take corrective actions such as adjusting fertilizer usage or improving soil quality. The inclusion of display units and alert mechanisms further enhances usability by providing instant feedback and notifications.

Overall, the proposed system offers a smart, efficient, and cost-effective solution for modern agriculture. It supports precision farming by ensuring optimal soil conditions, reducing resource wastage, and increasing crop productivity. The integration of IoT with soil monitoring systems represents a significant step toward sustainable and technology-driven agricultural practices [1][2].

2. REVIEW LITERATURE SURVEY

Recent advancements in smart agriculture have focused on automation and real-time monitoring using embedded systems and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies. Traditional soil testing methods rely on manual sampling and laboratory analysis, which are

time-consuming, costly, and do not provide real-time insights. These limitations often lead to improper fertilizer usage, poor soil management, and reduced agricultural productivity [1].

To overcome these challenges, several researchers have proposed sensor-based soil monitoring systems. Soil pH sensors and nutrient sensors are widely used to measure soil conditions directly in the field. These systems provide accurate readings; however, some implementations require complex hardware setups and frequent calibration, making them less suitable for small-scale farmers [2].

In recent years, IoT-based soil monitoring systems have gained significant attention. These systems use microcontrollers and sensors to collect real-time soil data and transmit it to cloud platforms for monitoring and analysis. Some studies have implemented Raspberry Pi-based systems integrated with advanced data analytics and machine learning techniques to predict soil fertility and crop suitability. While these approaches improve accuracy, they increase system complexity and cost [3].

Alternatively, ESP8266-based systems have been proposed as a simple, cost-effective, and efficient solution for soil monitoring. With built-in Wi-Fi capability, ESP8266 enables real-time data transmission without requiring additional communication modules. These systems are easy to deploy and suitable for both small and medium-scale agricultural applications.

Furthermore, wireless communication and IoT platforms have been widely used to provide real-time updates and alerts to farmers. Users can monitor soil conditions remotely through mobile or web applications, improving decision-making and resource management..

Based on the reviewed literature, it is evident that a combination of soil sensors, ESP8266, and IoT communication offers a low-cost, efficient, and reliable solution for real-time soil nutrient and pH monitoring. The proposed system builds upon these approaches to provide an optimized and practical implementation for smart agriculture [1][2][3][4].

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is designed to monitor soil nutrient levels and pH values using sensors, ESP8266 microcontroller, LCD display, and IoT communication. The methodology focuses on sensing soil parameters,

processing the data, and updating the information in real time.

A. System Design

The system consists of soil pH sensors and nutrient sensors placed in the soil to measure various parameters. These sensors are connected to the ESP8266, which acts as the central processing unit.

B. Data Acquisition

The continuously measure soil conditions such as pH level and nutrient content. The collected data reflects the current status of soil health.

C. Data Processing

The ESP8266 processes the sensor data and compares it with predefined threshold values. Based on this comparison, it determines whether the soil condition is optimal, acidic, or alkaline.

D. Display Unit

An I2C LCD module is used to display real-time information such as soil pH value and nutrient status. This allows users to monitor soil conditions locally.

E. Alert Mechanism

The system uses IoT communication to update soil data remotely. Users can access this information through a mobile or web dashboard, enabling real-time monitoring and alerts when soil conditions are not suitable.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system presents a smart and automated approach for soil monitoring using sensors, ESP8266, LCD display, and IoT technology. The system continuously measures soil pH and nutrient levels and provides real-time updates.

In this methodology, sensors are embedded in the soil to detect pH levels and nutrient conditions. When changes occur in soil properties, the sensors capture the data and send it to the ESP8266.

The ESP8266 acts as the central processing unit, analyzing the received data and comparing it with predefined threshold values to determine soil condition. Based on this analysis, the system identifies whether the soil is suitable for cultivation or requires treatment.

An I2C LCD module displays real-time soil data locally, allowing farmers to monitor conditions easily. Additionally, IoT connectivity enables remote access to soil data through web or mobile applications.

Whenever soil conditions change, the system updates the information instantly. This ensures accurate and

real-time monitoring, helping farmers take timely actions such as applying fertilizers or adjusting soil treatment.

The system operates continuously without manual intervention, making it suitable for modern precision agriculture.

WORKING PRINCIPLE

working principle of the proposed system is based on real-time sensing and monitoring of soil parameters. The system uses sensors to continuously measure soil pH levels and nutrient content.

Initially, the sensors detect soil conditions and generate corresponding electrical signals. These signals are sent to the ESP8266 microcontroller for processing.

The ESP8266 analyzes the sensor data and compares it with predefined threshold values to determine soil status. If the pH value is too high or too low, the system identifies the soil as alkaline or acidic, respectively.

The real-time soil status is displayed on the LCD module for local monitoring. At the same time, the system sends data to an IoT platform via Wi-Fi, allowing users to monitor soil conditions remotely.

The process is repeated continuously, ensuring accurate and up-to-date information. Thus, the system provides an efficient and automated solution for soil monitoring by combining sensing, processing, display, and communication technologies.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig 4.1: Block Diagram

5. RESULTS AND OUTCOMES

The proposed IoT-based soil monitoring system was successfully designed and implemented using soil sensors, ESP8266, LCD display, and IoT connectivity.

The system was tested under different soil conditions to evaluate its performance.

The sensors accurately measured soil pH levels and nutrient conditions. The ESP8266 processed the data efficiently and displayed real-time values on the LCD.

When soil conditions changed, the system updated the data instantly through IoT platforms, enabling real-time monitoring and quick decision-making.

Fig. 5.1: Output 1

Fig. 5.2: Output 2

The overall system performance was stable, accurate, and reliable. It reduced manual effort and provided continuous monitoring of soil health. The outcomes demonstrate that the system significantly improves agricultural efficiency and decision-making.

6. CONCLUSION

The proposed IoT-Based Soil Nutrient and pH Level Monitoring and Analyzing System using ESP8266 was successfully implemented and tested. The system effectively monitored soil conditions and provided real-time updates using sensor and IoT technologies.

The ESP8266 processed sensor data efficiently, while the LCD display enabled local monitoring. IoT functionality allowed remote access to soil information, improving farmer awareness and decision-making.

The system demonstrated reliable performance, reduced manual soil testing, and improved fertilizer

management. It is cost-effective and suitable for both small and large-scale farming applications.

In conclusion, the proposed system provides a smart, efficient, and scalable solution for modern agriculture. It highlights the importance of integrating IoT and embedded systems for precision farming and sustainable agricultural practices.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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